

MODERN APPROACH TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to modern methods and approaches to teaching a foreign language, their impact on the learning process and student results. The article analyzes the communicative approach, integration of modern technologies, individual methods and the development of intercultural communication competence in foreign language lessons, and considers the results. The analysis highlights the fact that modern technologies, including technical means, in teaching a foreign (English) language enrich the learning process and allow students to develop information and technical competence, as well as language skills, and motivate them. It is proved that modern methods are relevant in the educational environment for the successful preparation of students.

Keywords: pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, "Boomerang" method, foreign language, modern methods, communicative approach, educational technologies, individualization of learning, intercultural, communication, competence, teaching foreign languages.

1 Introduction

Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of professional education. Since specialists in various fields have a high rate of cooperation with foreign partners, there is a high demand for language learning among them.

The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the skills of choosing the most effective methods to achieve their goals are formed. In this case, the use of several methods of teaching and learning gives effective results. Teaching is carried out in small stages and is based on the student's existing knowledge system. As time progresses, innovations are increasing in every field.

Nowadays, we understand very well that improving the quality and efficiency of education is the basis of our future development. The teacher must approach his subject creatively during the lesson. The teacher must organize the lesson using modern pedagogical technologies and methods.

Currently, there is a growing interest in the use of pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process.

Currently, there are several types of interactive methods, and the educational process is being implemented using these methods. Pedagogical technology is a system of systematic actions that lead to previously planned results and are necessary.

There are many types of teaching methods. Students need to learn the information, understand the topic, and reinforce their knowledge through lectures, stories, explanations, and videos.

The teacher should use several methods that serve to consolidate educational information, help to understand it, and teach students to think about this topic. To increase students' vocabulary, work with books, learn to work with exercises related to tenses, phonetics in English. To develop students' activities, "debate", "circle", conversation, "pinboard", "business", brainstorming, presentation method, brainstorming method, "jigsaw" method, "Journey to the Land of Justice" method, "Bee colony" method, "Discussion-discussion" method, "Gallery" method, "Match grains" method, "Perception map" method, "Single circle" method and many other methods can be used in

the lesson process. The modern approach to foreign language teaching is focused on the active participation of students and aims to develop communication skills that allow them to apply language knowledge in real-life situations. Approaches such as feedback, cultural integration, and the use of authentic materials are widely used in teaching practice.

2 Methodology

We will analyze the fundamental principles of foreign language teaching, various methods of language teaching, as well as the impact of technology integration on the process of teaching German. An important aspect of the analysis is the digitalization of education in Uzbekistan and the development of professional competence of English teachers in modern educational conditions.

- *Integration of modern technical tools:* The use of online resources and digital tools in the learning process allows students to learn more interactively and effectively. Online platforms provide access to a variety of materials, including audio and video content.
- *Developing communication skills:* A communicative approach to learning helps develop the ability to communicate in English. Students learn to listen and understand through audio-visual aids and to express their thoughts and ideas in this way, using phrases, dialogues and role-plays.
- *Integration of cultural aspects:* The study of English culture and traditions becomes an integral part of education. The introduction of slides, subtitled films and short video lessons on customs and holidays helps students understand the language in a broader context and develop intercultural competence.
- *Individualized approach:* Using an individualized curriculum allows for the diverse needs of students to be taken into account. This contributes to more effective learning and better outcomes.

The above analysis confirms that the integration of modern technologies in foreign language lessons, various interactive methods, various innovative pedagogical technologies that develop listening, speaking, and communication competencies help to master the language more deeply and better. Students more successfully develop their language competence and can use the German language in real life. The didactic principles of learning, which are relevant in this era of multimedia development, as indicated by N. Gafurov and S. Osipov, namely, scientificity, availability, systematicity, relevance to practice, awareness and activity of students, and individualization in teaching, are an example of this. A. Parmonov also cites a number of factors that help to form information and technical competence in students, positive motivation in them, and educational activities [2]. K.D. Ushinsky cites such features as gradual adaptation to nature, compliance with psychological characteristics, regularity, and activity [3].

But his ideas about stratifying students, working with “high-quality” students complicate the goals a little. True, it is natural that when teaching through ICT, students will have problems with learning, falling behind, or students who do not have information and communicative competence. In such cases, taking measures to approach them individually depends on the skills of a modern foreign language teacher. In this case, with the help of independent work outside the classroom provided through an interactive and online platform (presentations, creating interactive tests, searching for information on the Internet, preparing projects, using ready-made electronic resources, using digital educational resources), the student works on himself and learns the lesson materials both independently and “forcedly”. [4].

Modern methods of teaching English show the following results: Students who engage in live dialogues, role-playing games and other communicative activities better demonstrate their language skills in communication. A foreign (English) language lesson with the integration of modern technologies becomes more interactive and interesting. Online resources and applications provide students with the opportunity to independently learn the language and deepen their knowledge at a convenient time for them. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as cooperative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a

person-oriented approach in the learning process, individualize teaching, taking into account the abilities of students, their level of knowledge acquisition and mastery [5].

Studying English culture and history allows students to better understand the language in context and develop intercultural competence, which is increasingly important in today's world [6].

It is important to note that a lesson that focuses on communication skills and the use of language in a real environment shows significant advantages. Students who participate in dialogues, role-playing, organizing real situations and other communicative exercises demonstrate a high level of language proficiency in communicating in English.

3 Conclusion

In conclusion, modern technologies are becoming an integral part of modern education. Therefore, modern methods require continuous professional development from teachers. Teachers must be prepared to integrate technology into lessons, adapt teaching materials, and create a stimulating learning environment, as well as be able to motivate students' needs and expectations in adapting to a changing environment. The use of multimedia creates conditions for students to obtain information from newspapers, magazines, television, work with films and videos, independently prepare interviews, use authentic materials, and at the same time contribute to conducting teleconferences. All this shows that modern technologies are important for meeting the needs of students in an innovative educational environment.

In general, a modern approach to teaching German, namely using multimedia, organizing lessons focused on communication skills and using the language in a real environment, has a positive effect on students' deeper understanding and use of the language, developing communication skills and cultural competence, and at the same time making the learning process more interesting.

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